

Rimini Declaration

Declaration on Reproducibility and Objective Measurability of Performances in AI and Robotics Research

Background

We are in the middle of a ‘reproducibility crisis’ affecting many research fields¹.

The causes are various. In other fields the causes can often be distorted consequences of the ‘publish or perish’ culture and dubious hiring and career progression practices, privileging brute quantitative metrics over the evaluation of the actual contributions of the researchers from a scientific content point of view².

The situation in robotics is peculiar as reproducibility and objective measures of results have not even been agreed. This emphasizes the negative effects of the regressive processes at play in most research fields. Benchmarking pushes forward the definition of “standardized” approaches to robot system design that eventually lead to progresses in modularity, transferability (across applications and across robotic platforms) and compositionality that are missing today and hamper the development of more complex commercial robot systems.

The situation severely impairs both basic research progress and technology transfer aka innovation. It can lead and has led to dramatic investment backlashes like in the case of the ‘self-driving car’³. The technology transfer of robotics results into new products and services is stagnating⁴. Attempts to have a ‘structured dialogue’ between ‘academia’ and ‘industry’ have mitigated, but not overcome the problem. We believe that we need a common scientific and technical ground to be able to assess the real problems solved and opportunity to cope with societal needs opened by new research. We believe that the massive investment failure in ‘self-driving cars’ and the premature shift of the Eu framework programs from basic research to innovation originate from the same ‘optimistic’ evaluation of the state of the art in AI and Robotics made possible by the weak reproducibility and benchmarking practices in the community.

¹Menke, J., Roelandse, M., Ozyurt, B., Martone, M. & Bandrowski, A. Preprint at bioRxiv <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.01.15.908111> (2020)

²Albertyn, C. The legacy of the reproducibility crisis. *Nat Rev Psychol* 2, 590 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44159-023-00236-2>

³ <https://www.ft.com/content/345c1dfd-b08c-44b6-81b4-c0bf8a46a43f>

⁴ Linden, A., Fenn, J., Understanding gartner’s hype cycles, Strategic Analysis Report No R-20-1971. Gartner, Inc, 2003

Today only the IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine has in place a clear process for reproducible articles⁵. Only recently a dedicated project for benchmarking locomotion, Eurobench⁶, has been funded by the EU Commission. The Commission has also funded, back in 2013, 2 coordination actions on benchmarking competitions, RoCKIn⁷ and eurAthlon, that paved the way for using research competitions as a means to compare different approaches to common research problems, represented by the competition league challenges, and lead to the current European Robotics League (ERL). Despite those little steps forward and the request of having clear benchmarking processes defined in project proposals in Robotics put in place by the EU commission since H2020, still reproducibility and benchmarking practices are not mainstream in the research community.

Principles

- Reproducibility and objective measurability of results (aka benchmarking) are basic requisites of the scientific methodology. Modern engineering is ‘the application of scientific knowledge to solve human needs’.
- Reproducibility is not mainstream in AI and Robotics: it should be.
- We need to agree on a few simple procedures (like those regulating the R-articles in IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine⁸).
- We need to develop operational procedures to compare different robots’ functionalities (aka ‘benchmarks’).
- We need to adopt at least one existing benchmark where they are available (there are already many).
- We need to link reproducibility, benchmarks, competitions and challenges.

Call to Action

- ❖ Let’s adopt rigorous reproducibility and benchmarking methodologies in our own research.

⁵ Bonsignorio, F., A New Kind of Article for Reproducible Research in Intelligent Robotics [From the Field], in IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 178-182, Sept. 2017, doi: 10.1109/MRA.2017.2722918.

⁶ Torricelli, D., Pons, J.L. (2019). EUROBENCH: Preparing Robots for the Real World. In: Carrozza, M., Micera, S., Pons, J. (eds) Wearable Robotics: Challenges and Trends. WeRob 2018. Biosystems & Biorobotics, vol 22. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-01887-0_72

⁷ RoCKIn: Benchmarking Through Robot Competitions, P. U. Lima (Editor), InTechOpen, 2017 <https://www.intechopen.com/books/6279>

⁸ IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine, R-article authors’ guidelines, online: <https://www.ieee-ras.org/publications/ram/information-for-authors-ram/reproducible-articles-r-articles-short-replication-articles-r-articles-reply-articles>

- ❖ Let's require rigorous reproducibility and benchmarking methodologies when we review papers and projects.
- ❖ Let's support the creation of 'reproducible research tracks' in the journals to which we cooperate as editors or associated editors.
- ❖ Let's promote the growth of robot research competitions as single events or as part of major conferences, yet another way of presenting and benchmarking research results, not just in the traditional paper presentation format but by tackling a common problem by different groups from different academic and industry institutions.
- ❖ Let's maintain a list of publishing venues allowing managing a reproducible research process.
- ❖ Let's maintain a repository of benchmarks for the areas of AI and robotics where they exist and a gap list about the areas or the task sets for which benchmarks are not available.

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